

Association between interleukin-18(TG) "rs 19465189" gene polymorphism and Helicobacter pylori infection in the southern of Iraq (Nasiriyah Province)

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ABSTRACT

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The study's was conducted in the south of Iraq (Nasiriyah Province), to detect relationship between (IL-18) gene polymorphism and H. pylori infections from the period 10/1/2021 to 1/3/2022, where 100 blood samples were collected H. pylori patients for the purpose of DNA extraction and identification of interleukin-18 polymorphisms . The results were as follows: The demographic and mdicale features of a whole of (100) patients were considered in this study, involving aged, sex, mean body weight, smoking, alcohol use, education, income level, and related to stomach cancer. There were 35 women and 65 men in the study group, respectively. The percentage of infection was highest in the population in rural areas, where the mean age was 53.9 10.8 years. Sequencing was performed on 30 randomly selected blood samples, and the results revealed that none of the samples had changed., Also found In this study the mutant heterozygous (TG) "rs 19465189" were associated with higher levels of IL-18 and severe gastric inflammation compared with other genotypes .The results of sequencing by Macrogen Corporation, were uis alised V.7.2.6 program by Bioedit, as well as and we made alignment using Clustal Omega tool available online. the results showed there was compatibility between recorded wolrd gene bank IL-18 polymorphism with IL-18 polymorphism in H. pylori patients in studied area.

KEYWORDS:

interleukin-18(TG) "rs 19465189" gene, Helicobacter infection, Iraq

INTRODUCTION

Helicobacter pylori :

In 1982, Marshall and Warren [65] discovered H. pylori, marking the beginning of a new era for stomach microbiology. The separation of H. pylori, along with a rising popularity in the pathogenesis of gastroduodenal illnesses and the relatively simple accessibility of clinical samples such as through endoscopic biopsy, have led to major progress in medicine treatment regardless of the fact that spiral organisms was already discovered in the gastric mucus layer numerous already in the last century. The aim of this work is to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the increasingly massive literature on Helicobacter pylori pertaining to specific elements of medical microbial science. We discuss

advancements in detecting the presence of H. pylori and strategies for distinguishing between different forms of H. pylori, as well as the background for effective infection treatment. In addition, we'll go over H. heilmanii, which has been identified as a rare cause of gastritis in people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

On 10/1/2021, I began collecting samples for patients suffering from H. pylori infection, as work began on collecting samples at Al-Rifai Hospital after All procedures for sample collection have been completed.

Its purpose is to know the number of infected people in the city of Al-Rifai/ Dhi Qar governorate, the relationship of IL-18 to the injured and the extent of its impact and effectiveness. Where 2 moles of blood were taken for each infected patient and 2 moles of blood for the non-infected, where the total number was 100 positive samples and 100 other negative samples, and the sample was collected in an anticoagulant tube, After I finish collecting samples for the day, I put the collected samples in the freezer. The sample collection process took 3 months, then the samples were taken to the Al-Amal lab in the city of Najaf with the aim of

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conducting a PCR examination for them. The samples were examined and the results were good. Then the genetic

sequencing examination of 30 samples was carried out, and the work took about 3-4 months.

Table (2:3) Primers used in this study

Target gene		Sequence (5'-3')	Ta (°C)	Product size	Reference
IL-18	F	GGTCAGTCTTTGCTATCA TTCCAGG	60	290 bp	
	R	CCCCTTCCTCCCAAGCTCAAT			

Figure (3-5): RedSafe nucleic acid staining solution agarose gel of monplex PCR amplified products from whole blood extracted DNA and amplified with IL-18 genes primers

The electrophoresis was carried out for 1 hour at 75 volts. Lane (M) is a DNA molecular size marker (100 bp ladder), and Lanes (1-15 are diffrant sampls) have positive IL-18 findings (290bp).

Figure (3-6): RedSafe nucleic acid staining solution agarose gel of monplex PCR amplified products from whole blood extracted DNA and amplified with IL-18 gene primers. For 1 hour, the electrophoresis was run at 75 volts. Lane (M) is a DNA molecular size marker (100 bp ladder), and Lanes (16- 24 are diffrant sampls) have IL-18 positive results (290bp).

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Figure (3-7): RedSafe nucleic acid staining solution agarose gel of monplex PCR amplified products from whole blood extracted DNA and amplified with IL-18 genes primers The electrophoresis was carried out for 1 hour at 75 volts. Lane (M) shows positive results with IL-18. Lanes (25- 39 are diffrant sampls) indicate positive results with IL-18 (290bp).

Figure (3-8): RedSafe nucleic acid staining solution agarose gel of monplex PCR amplified products from whole blood extracted DNA and amplified with IL-18 genes primers

The electrophoresis was carried out for 1 hour at 75 volts. Lane (M): DNA molecular size marker (100 bp ladder); Lanes (40,42,43,44,45,46,47, and 50 are diffrant sampls): positive results with IL-18 (290bp); Lanes (41,48,49,51,52,53, and 54): was not worked with IL-18 (290bp).

The first identified segment of the Interleukin-18 gene has a size of 290 base pairs (290 bp) and the location of this region of the whole gene in the UTR 3 (Untranslated region) after exon 5 of the gene.

This region extends in relation to the gene from position 24331 to 24621 depending on the transcript Reference Copy registered in the NCBI Gene Bank under accession number EF444989.

Fragment "A"		Product size
Forward	5'-GGTCAGTCTTTGCTATCATTCCAGG-3'	290
Reverse	5'-CCCCTTCCTCCCAAGCTCAAT-3'	

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Fig.(3.9) Alignment Results for "A" Fragment by Bioedit Program V.7.2.6 [290 bp].

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Table.(3-10) Alignment Results for "A" Fragment by Clustal Omega

A1_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A2_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A3_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A4_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A5_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A6_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A7_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A8_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A9_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A10_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A11_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A12_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A13_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A14_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A15_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A16_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A17_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A18_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A19_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60
A20_AF	GGATAGTTGATACAGGCCATTAAGATTTACTTTTCAGTGGAACAGGAGTCCATTTTCATA	60

A1_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A2_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A3_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A4_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A5_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A6_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A7_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A8_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A9_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A10_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A11_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A12_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A13_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A14_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A15_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A16_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A17_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A18_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A19_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120
A20_AF	AAACTTCTTTATCTGCTGTATCAGATGCAAGCCACACGGATACCATCATTAGAATTTTAT	120

A1_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A2_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A3_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A4_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A5_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A6_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A7_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A8_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A9_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A10_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A11_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A12_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A13_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A14_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A15_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A16_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A17_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A18_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A19_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180
A20_AF	TTAATAATTTTACACTTTCTGCAACAGAAAGTAAGCTTGGGGAGAGGGATACCAAAT	180

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Table(3.10) Alignment Results for "A" Fragment by Clustal Omega

A1_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A2_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A3_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A4_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A5_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A6_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A7_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A8_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A9_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A10_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A11_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A12_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A13_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A14_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A15_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A16_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A17_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A18_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A19_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240
A20_AF	CAGGTAAGAGGGCAAATATTTACTTGCAGTTCCAGTGTAAAACTTTCTATTCTCGGAA	240

A1_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A2_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A3_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A4_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A5_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A6_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A7_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A8_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A9_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A10_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A11_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A12_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A13_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A14_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A15_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A16_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A17_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A18_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A19_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290
A20_AF	TGATAGCAAAGACTGACCTAAAAATATTTGAAATACAATTTAAGGATACAT	290

4.1. Discussion:

This research would include (100) subject matters & characterized demographic and medical features like age, gender, mean body mass, smoking, drinking habits, schooling, level of income, and position in relation to gastric

cancer. The research team included 65 males (65%), compared to 35 females (35%). The mean lifespan has been 53.9 ±10.8 years. And It is striking that through collecting samples and observing the percentage of infection, it was noted that the percentage of infection in the inhabitants of

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villages and rural areas is higher than the percentage of cities, And In other studies, infection with bacteria was generally observed in childhood, with ulcers appearing later in life. In fact, nearly half of all 12 US adults over the age of 60 are infected with *H. pylori*, but only a small percentage of those infected develop ulcers. However, the situation in Saudi Arabia is different from the situation in the United States and other developed countries.

And, according to a study performed in the KSA , the overall prevalence in the younger aged group seems to be similar to many other research in KSA , but scientists in the southern area of KSA demonstrated that now the prevalence rate of *Helicobacter pylori* infection seems to be nearly the same in various ages groups. When compared to girls patient populations, with us female patients had a higher incidence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection (70percent). (58 percent). Neither any native research was able to demonstrate this female predominance of *Helicobacter pylori* infections. It could be a coincidence, or it could necessitate some other research with a bigger sample size. In our PUD patient populations, the proportion of nonsmokers has been relatively high 111 (84.1percent) than that of people who smoke 21 (15.9 percent). As just a consequence, the smoking rate and PUD has produced a contradictory results. This could be linked to the fact that smoking seems to be more constrained in the KSA than in other countries. In comparison to the amount of people who smoke between many PUD patients, *H. pylori* infection was much more prevalent in smokers (61 percent) than in nonsmokers (52 percent). Several more local and international researches have found a link between smoking & *Helicobacter pylori* infections.

Most of the studies that have been conducted in various countries have been the incidence of *H. pylori* infection is variable through various ages or through the physical structure of people or through the economic status of some of them and this is observed in several countries in Africa, for example.

Also Infectious diseases are more prevalent in underdeveloped countries. 90 percent of the adult population in nations with poor sanitation can be infected.

Infection is currently far less common in Australia than it was in the past, especially among the younger people.

For example, in another study in Australia, *H. pylori* is found in approximately 40% of Australians over the age of 60. *H. pylori* infection is more common in indigenous Australians than in non-indigenous Australians. *H. pylori* is also more prevalent in particular ethnic groups (e.g. Middle Eastern, Asian and eastern European). The infection rate does not differ between males and women.

the focus of this research was to see if there was a link between Interlikeun-18 gene polymorphisms and *H. pylori* infection susceptibility .

The major immune cell reaction in stomach mucosa caused by *Helicobacter pylori* infection has been associated with the

production of several pro inflammatory cytokines related to the growth of *Helicobacter pylori* associated illnesses. [109,114].

Interleukin-18, which is typically producing via activated monocytes/macrophages in the local ecosystem, seems to be an important pro inflammatory cytokine that's been noticed in several facets of inflammation and Th1 reactions [115,117], and also was risen in *Helicobacter pylori* infections [119,126]. The preponderance of *Helicobacter pylori* infection differs by country. The severity and category of *Helicobacter pylori*-associated inflammation and illnesses change based on whether the province has a rising or falling prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infections [109,110]. As a result, both genes and ecosystem factors may play a role in the vulnerability and actual result of *H. pylori* infection. Various vulnerability genes and external conditions strongly affect *Helicobacter pylori* infections, and no single gene or external factors has a major impact on vulnerability to *Helicobacter pylori* infections [118,126] .

In this study found mutant heterozygous (AC) " rs 1946519 genotype " and (TG) "rs 19465189" were associated with higher levels of IL-18 and severe gastric inflammation compared with other genotypes , While in other study found , When tried to compare to certain other genetic variants in *Helicobacter pylori*-infected patient populations, the CC genotype at location "607A/C" as well as the GG genotype at location "137G/C" have been associated with higher levels of Interleukin-18 and serious stomach inflammation. [125,126] As a result, Interleukin-18 genetic variations could modify the capabilities of Interleukin-18 producing and might even take an active part in host vulnerability and the results of *Helicobacter pylori* infection, which will necessitate numerous additional researches.

Yet another research [125] found that even in the Iranian population, the pervasiveness of the AA genotype as Well as A allele at position "607C/A", although not at location "137G/C", have been substantially lower in *Helicobacter pylori*-infected duodenal ulcer patient populations than in *Helicobacter pylori*-negative subjects for interleukin-18 promoter polymorphisms at locations "137G/C and 607C/A". This disparity could be linked to a variety of variables, such as ethnic variability in interleukin-18 genotype dispersion, that also varies across racial communities, sample size, medical heterogeneity, as well as the types of external factors involved in the pathogenesis of *H. pylori* infection.

Another study on just an *Helicobacter. pylori*-infected Korean sample of the people The haplotype frequency bands have been used to study the genetic connection among these 5 SNPs, as well as the haplotype analysis revealed that such protecting haplotype CGT (137C/ + 113G/ + 127T) was much more common in the *Helicobacter pylori* negatively groups than that of the *Helicobacter. Pylori* positively groups.

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The above findings imply that all these three loci could have a synergistic impact on Helicobacter pylori infections. More workable study on such SNPs has been needed.

With us research results were still not definitive as it must be determined regardless of whether there's no substantial differences or whether the sample size seems to be insufficient to find out the variations. Helicobacter pylori subjects seem to be scarce, particularly in mid-aged or seniors healthcare cohorts.

It's the first study to look at the link among gene changes in the Interleukin-18 gene as well as vulnerability to Helicobacter. pylori infections in a highly populated. Our research, even so, has many constraints.

Initially, our research population seemed to be limited, which could have influenced a few of the findings, particularly the absence of connection among Helicobacter pylori associating specific illness phenotypes. Second, humans didn't even look into the relationship among Interleukin-18 level and Interleukin-18 Genetic polymorphism. Third, with us research was limited to a specific community. Finally, neither any extra reproduction with an unbiased testing carried out. As a consequence, large scale, good designed research must be regarded in order to verify our findings, avert selection bias like potential racial disparities, and protect against the bias of repeating testing impacts.

As observe the effectiveness of interleukin-18, its activity, its role in enhancing immunity, and the percentages that we notice increase when there are any changes that occur, especially when an infection occurs, as is the case in infection with H pylori infection .

When we observe healthy people and the level of interleukin 18, and when we observe others infected with H pylori infection , we notice an increase in the levels of interleukin (18) Perhaps the occurrence of a polymorphism in interleukin 18 gives a high genetic. predisposition to infection with Helicobacter pylori infection, but the severity of infection is low, that is, not severe. And H. pylori infection is one of the causes of interleukin 18 polymorphism and It should be known that people with H. pylori who have interleukin-18 polymorphism have a genetic predisposition compared to people who do not have interleukin-18 polymorphism.

Inflammatory cells infiltrate the stomach mucosa after infection with Helicobacter pylori, and their migration and activation are thought to be dependent on H. pylori-induced generation of proinflammatory cytokines [127].

We expected that IL-18 would play a role in the process because the Th1 response is thought to be prevalent in H. pylori-infected gastric mucosa. However, the impact of H. pylori infection on IL-18 production is unknown, as one study found that antral, but not corporal, Interleukin-18 mRNA levels were up-regulated during H. pylori infection [128],

while another found that mucosal Interleukin-18 mRNA levels were unaffected by H. pylori infection [129].

T lymphocytes, thymocytes, and natural killer cells are all affected by IL-12, which increases the production of Interleukin -18 receptors. The role of Interleukin-18 in the polarizations of the Th1 reaction appears to be reliant on the expression of the IFN- and IL-12 receptor 2 chains. In cytokine biology, the generation of IFN- γ by the mixture of IL-18 and Interleukin-12 was an instance of real synergisms, identical to the synergisms of Interleukin-1 and TNF- in inflammation replicas.

Even though IFN- γ was the "signature" cytokine of "CD4+ & CD8+ T "cell, and normal cell. IFN- γ production is thought to be responsible for much of IL-18's biology . All the results that we observe are positive, for example, gene 350,

all results were positive except for sample No. 19, and this is a very high percentage indicating the extent of its effectiveness. While we note in the 290 gene also the high positive percentage, except for samples 41, 48, 49, 51, 52, 53 and 54 only, it was do not work with interleukin 18 gene 290 . Through studies, we note that H. pylori infection regulates the production of interleukin-18, that interleukin-18 contributes significantly to the processes of immune regulation, and we note the increase that occurs and this is clear in the above results,

Interleukin-18 values were observed in gastric mucosal biopsy samples and also separated gastric endothelial cell & mononuclear cells from the basal lamina.

Interleukin-18 levels in gastric epithelial cell and the monocyte cells line THP-1 result is a unique with Helicobacter pylori have been evaluated. Helicobacter pylori-infected epithelial cell and monocytes reported to produce more Interleukin-18 in both systems. Gastric mucosa diseased with Helicobacter pylori, the degree of gastric inflammation was tightly connected to Interleukin-18 levels, suggesting that Helicobacter pylori-induced Interleukin-18 shows a substantial part in stomach damage.

Interleukin-18's function in H. pylori-induced inflammation in humans is not well defined. Despite mature Interleukin-18 protein is present in both infected and non - infected individuals' mucosa, thus according to Tomita et al. [130], antral Interleukin-18 mRNA levels were increased in Helicobacter pylori infections.

Interleukin-18 production is related with antral H. pylori infection as assessed by immunohistochemistry, According to Fera et al. [131], Interleukin-18 mRNA is produced regardless to H. pylori infections.

The cause of the disparity is unknown; however, one explanation could be the nonquantitative character of mRNA and protein level analyses.

Despite the fact that the exact mechanism and pathogenic processes underlying H.pylori-related illnesses remain unknown, studies confirm that these diseases are also

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influenced by stimulated immune reactions, with inflammatory responses impacted by both ecological and host genetic factors. Infection with *H. pylori* triggers signaling pathways processes in the stomach mucosa, which help in the formation of pro inflammatory cytokine & certain others associated gene, as well as the switch to the T-helper1 (Th1) responses. (3,4,5,6) .

SNPs of putative genes implicated in the immune and inflammatory responses have been examined extensively as genetic variables that confer *H. pylori* infections vulnerability. Moreover, a connection between Interleukin-18 gene polymorphisms & *Helicobacter pylori* infections sensitivity was yet to be established.

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